

T_m shift analysis

Make up protein solution to 2 μ M in 10mM Hepes, 50mM HEPES pH7.5

Add 1:1000 dilution of Sypro orange to 2.2ml of protein solution per plate.

Pipette 0.5 μ l of compound into the bottom of a 96 well PCR plate.

Pipette 19.5 μ l of protein into the wells.

Seal with optically active plate seals.

Spin down for 1 minute.

Run a thermal scan on an RT-PCR machine cycling from 20°C to 95°C over the course of 24 minutes.

Analyse results using excel and graph pad prism to integrate lines to find the midpoint and thus the T_m shift. DMSO only and Water controls embedded in the plate used to calculate reference cells from which to base the T_m shift from.

ALK2:

2 plates set up in duplicate however the machine used seized up half way through the first run so the second run had to be moved to the second machine after the RIPK2 plates were run, and thus there was only one set of results and it had been sitting around (covered) for longer than ideal.

RIPK2:

2 plates set up in duplicate and run sequentially on the RT-PCR machine.

Results can be seen below:

For ALK2, shifts above 12 °C are of considerable interest while for RIPK2 this number is much lower, closer to 8 °C.

Tm shift results for ALK2

Tm shift results for RIPK2 (1)

Tm shift results for RIPK2 (1)

K115A Tm shift RIPK2 repeat comparison

Comparison of the two RIPK2 results shows high variance between the two runs.